

Project No. 964220

Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment

Deliverable 7.3

User guidelines for clinicians and scientific dissemination

WP 7 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation

Authors	Lina Plataniti, Ira Haraldsen, Vebjørn Andersson (OUS), Cindy Birck (AE), Joanna Plesniak (accelCH)
Lead participant	OUS
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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
CRF	Case Report Form
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EEG	Electroencephalography
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Practitioner
H2020	Horizon 2020
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
MCI	Mild Cognitive Impairment
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MEG	Magnetic Encephalography
ML	Machine Learning
NPT	Neuropsychological Test
WP	Work Package

Partner Short Names

OUS	Oslo University Hospital
AALTO	Aalto University
accelCH	accelopment Schweiz AG
AE	Alzheimer Europe
Brainsymph	BrainSymph AS
DNV	Det Norske Veritas
HUS	Helsinki University Hospital
IRCCS	Scientific Institute for Research, Hospitalization and Healthcare, San Raffaele Roma
Lurtis	Lurtis Rules S.L
Neuroconnect	Neuroconnect Srl
OsloMET	Oslo Metropolitan University
Radboudumc	Radboud University Medical Center
TLU	Tallinn University

UCM	Complutense University of Madrid
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

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1 Executive Summary

The aim of deliverable 7.3 is to create the outline of the material that will support the use and decision-making of clinicians with regards to the AI-Mind tools. It is important to provide clinicians and other healthcare professionals with the tools that will facilitate the transition from the classical diagnostic methods to the modern-technology diagnostics of the future. To achieve this, we have not only to inform clinicians, but also to supply them with guidelines and tools that are easily accessible and understandable.

This report provides an overall set of information expanding from knowledge-base for the AI-Mind technology to user manuals and starter kits for the AI-Mind tools. The intention is to disseminate the scientific results produced by AI-Mind, as part of this informative set. The clinicians' knowledge-base is built through educational material, which includes the AI-Mind educational programme, and a series of toolboxes that cover all disciplines relevant to the work of clinicians and other healthcare professionals. It also includes courses, webinars, interactive meetings, networks, as well as openly available reports and literature. The user manuals include detailed guidelines on the use of the developed AI-Mind tools. A preliminary outline of the manuals is presented here; the final version will be ready by the end of the project. The user starter kits are delivered as a two-step process: initially as a study starter kit, designed to cover the needs of the AI-Mind clinical study; this will be improved and evolve throughout the project, leading to the final user starter kit (deliverable 7.7, M60).

This deliverable is the first report produced under task 7.3. Its content will be updated throughout the project. The final version will be submitted as deliverable 7.8 at the end of the project (M60).

2 Introduction

The AI-Mind solution will include two innovative Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based tools hosted in a new advanced platform, with the ambition to provide clinicians with a powerful means of identifying brain dysconnectivity and predicting the risk of developing dementia:

- The AI-Mind Connector: a tool that will use electroencephalography (EEG) data combined with AI algorithms to create an automated functional brain connectivity map; this may reveal novel biomarkers of early brain network disturbances in people with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI).
- The AI-Mind Predictor: a tool that will use the outcome of Connector combined with measurements of cognitive function, genetics, blood protein levels, and demographic data, which will feed an AI algorithm for dementia risk prediction.
- The AI-Mind Platform: an innovative cloud-based platform where the final tools will be hosted and run (i.e. AI-Mind Connector & Predictor, the software and AI algorithms).

Providing easily accessible and comprehensible user guidelines will facilitate the uptake and use of the AI-Mind technology by all AI-Mind stakeholders. Comprehensive educational programs, along with practical information and user-support, intrigue the interest and boost the use of the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor.

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the means that clinicians, other healthcare providers, and healthcare managers may access in order to get information and guidelines that will highly motivate them to understand and use the AI-Mind tools. The objective is to explain and facilitate the transition from the current, traditional clinical procedures to the digital, AI-based diagnostics of the future. In addition, the provided material will support decision-making and communication with patients, especially in cases with a high-risk predictive result.

The material presented here expands from the familiarisation with the tools and the science behind them, to the legal aspects of data sharing, the trustworthiness of AI-based medical devices, the interpretation of results and the communication with the patient, as described in *Figure 1*. The intention is to create the best approach for the use of AI-Mind tools and to support the clinical decision-making based on the outcomes of the tools, as well as the communication with the patients, especially when there is a predictive diagnosis of developing dementia.

Figure 1: The span of information for clinicians

This information is presented in the chapters below segregated as “Educational material” for the educational background, “User Manual” providing the detailed usage guide for AI-Mind Connector and Predictor, and the “AI-Mind starter kit” incorporating all the basics to start using the AI-Mind tools.

Scientific dissemination and user guidelines for clinicians: the scientific publications produced in AI-Mind will serve as background information for the project’s educational tool-specific program for internal and later external clinicians and healthcare providers.

3 Educational material (knowledge-base)

To safeguard the best usage of the developed AI-Mind Connector and Predictor, the AI-Mind project has the ambition to provide the educational background and design optimal guidelines for clinicians and healthcare professionals. The learning experience is offered through two different approaches: the “Educational user guideline programme” (on-site and online material) and the “Educational user guideline toolboxes” (online material). The toolboxes integrate material from the educational guideline programme that can be offered online.

3.1 Educational User Guideline Programme

AI-Mind’s educational guideline programme includes courses, lectures, webinars, and networking activities. The material is available either internally or publicly. All material will be given or lectured in the AI-Mind clinical partners' languages (Finish, Italian, Norwegian, Spanish) and English. Primarily, this deliverable focuses on the AI-Mind member states’ clinicians and healthcare professionals, but may attract as well other broader stakeholder groups. Consequently, all material will be potentially translated as well to English. The intended audience is defined according to the content and objectives of each activity.

Courses: a series of courses is prepared on specific necessary guideline topics for specific audiences. Such courses aim at providing increased hands-on understanding of AI-Mind Connector and Predictor using empowered EEG/MEG, offering case supervision and potentially individual data sharing, etc. Such courses include seminars, discussion and supervision groups, and interactive lectures. They may involve national or international audience beyond the AI-Mind partner organisations, and may be held as online, hybrid or in-person events - as part of the AI-Mind events (see D7.2). As an example, a two-day course is developed by OUS in cooperation with the Norwegian Medical Association, aiming at informing General Practitioners (GPs) on how to improve the future MCI diagnostics by the use of AI-Mind Connector and Predictor, how to mediate necessary mathematical understanding and to explain the limitations and uncertainties of the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor techniques. Furthermore, this course trains GPs on selecting the right candidates for such screening investigations (see Annex I).

Use Case and Guideline Lectures & Webinars: organised independently or during AI-Mind events. Scientific advisors, consortium members, and actors from project collaborations, e.g. EBRAINS, will be invited to give additional lectures and seminars with complementary knowledge transfer with regard to the practical use of the AI-Mind tools. The intended audience will be variable depending on the topic: clinicians, healthcare providers, procurement departments, EEG technicians, engineers, etc.

Interviews: interviews with consortium members and other stakeholders, sharing their working experience and future needs while developing the AI-Mind tools. The content of such interviews is both informative and motivating, guaranteeing a successful future use of the AI-Mind technology.

PhD & Young Researcher Club: A network for PhD students and young researchers working in the AI-Mind project. The purpose of the network is to teach hands-on knowledge across the consortium’s

interdisciplinary teams and to prevent developmental flaws that may occur due to limited cross-subject expert knowledge.

End-of-project, on-site training to clinicians: the consortium plans to organise hands-on training courses in the four countries where the clinical study takes place (Finland, Italy, Norway, and Spain) to demonstrate the use of AI-Mind Predictor and Connector. The training sessions will be designed for local clinicians (GPs, neurologists, etc.), and will be organised only as physical events, aiming at attracting the broader attention of the local communities.

The material provided by AI-Mind’s educational user guideline programme will be developed in accordance with the project's communication and dissemination plan (D7.2). These specific user guidelines activities will be organised in toolboxes. The toolboxes will be available in a knowledge hub, hosted on the project’s website, indicating the discipline, purpose, and intended audience.

3.2 Educational Toolboxes

The educational programme will be organised in toolboxes, communicated both with on-site and online activities and material. The educational toolboxes provide carefully selected and developed material that the interdisciplinary AI-Mind stakeholders may access to understand the background when evaluating and using the AI-Mind tools. The toolboxes cover all disciplines involved in the development of AI-Mind Connector and Predictor, including: medical, engineering, data management, ethical algorithm testing, and decision-making procedures. They are designed in a way that allows easy access and interaction across the borders of the AI-Mind member states. *Figure 2* presents an overview of the AI-Mind guideline toolboxes.

Figure 2: Overview of the AI-Mind educational guideline toolboxes

All educational material may be adjusted throughout the project in order to be enriched with new information and to reflect upcoming, yet unknown, needs. Detailed information for the toolboxes per discipline is presented below, describing the aim, audience, content, the already available and planned material.

3.2.1 Medical Expertise

Toolboxes offering material on the main conditions investigated in AI-Mind: MCI and Dementia, as well as on the innovative medical tools: Digital Cognitive testing and Genetic biomarkers. The main target group of these tools are clinicians and other healthcare professionals.

Toolbox on Medical Expertise

Aim	To provide the medical background for the classical and future, AI-supported medical decision making in MCI
Audience	Clinicians, nurses, neuropsychologists, patient organisations and other healthcare professionals
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of MCI and classical clinical investigation procedures • Description of known dementia risk factors • General information on risk assessment of developing dementia • What is AI and how it can be used in the clinical daily routines • How to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ interpret the result & ○ communicate it with the patient. • Limitations and possibilities of traditional and new biomarkers
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web-based open source material (reports and other) • AI-Mind: “Report map of MCI diagnostics and management” (Deliverable 1.1)
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses/seminars on-site, hybrid and online

Toolbox on Digital Cognitive Testing

Aim	To inform about the digital cognitive testing
Audience	Clinicians, neuropsychologists, other healthcare professionals, and patient organisations
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digitalised cognitive tests, general info, overview of available tools • Effectiveness of digital cognitive tests • Acceptance by professionals and patients in introducing digital cognitive testing in clinical practice gathered through activities such as reviews, surveys and interviews
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material provided by external partners • Educational literature on the digital cognitive testing used in AI-Mind

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training sessions • AI-Mind: “Report map of MCI diagnostics and management” (Deliverable 1.1)
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-site, hybrid courses/seminars, and webinars • Videos of courses/seminars • Simulation videos of digital cognitive tests

Toolbox on traditional and new biomarkers in the field of MCI

Aim	To inform about the genetic and biomarker analysis used in AI-Mind
Audience	Clinicians, other healthcare professionals, researchers, patient organisations
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The genetic and protein metabolism links to dementia • Possibilities and limitations of visual technologies as biomarkers of MCI and dementia • Background information on plasma tau proteins and new assays on plasma p-tau analyses
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External scientific publications on the known genetics and metabolic preconditioning of dementia
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses/seminars on-site, hybrids and webinars

3.2.2 Explainability and Ethics

The results of AI-Mind tools are based on the outcome of AI algorithms. To safeguard the reliability of the results, the AI algorithms must be trustworthy. The clinicians must be aware of the technical limitations and uncertainty of the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor to make a final responsible decision for their patients. Furthermore, each patient must be sufficiently informed about the implications of the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor use. Ethical dimensions of using both AI-Mind tools have to be reflected on and discussed among health professionals, patient organisations, and unofficial national patient fora. Ethical reflection includes broader societal implications. It is anticipated that the users of AI-Mind Connector and Predictor trust the technologies and positively implement them into a responsible doctor-patient relationship. This toolbox provides the necessary background for this purpose.

Toolbox on Ethics and Trustworthiness of AI-based medical devices

Aim	To inform about AI-Mind Connector and Predictor’s explainability and ethical considerations. To inform about the technical trustworthiness of both tools.
Audience	Clinicians, patient organisations, politicians, healthcare managers, informal national patient representatives, and all AI-Mind stakeholders
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European regulations on the use of AI • Human Rights and other legal aspects • AI-Mind project results • Technical explainability & uncertainties

	All topics presented in a language understandable by the audience
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European and international guidelines on AI trustworthiness • Literature • AI-Mind: “AI-Medical Device software compliance requirements map” (Deliverable 1.2)
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses/seminars on-site, hybrid and online • Open days in hospitals • AI-Mind deliverables

3.2.3 Engineering

The engineering disciplines involved in the AI-Mind project are expected to be interesting for clinicians and healthcare providers, in addition to stakeholders working in the specific fields, including AI algorithm development and electroencephalography (EEG). The toolboxes below aim at providing the necessary background to help clinicians understand the engineering of AI-Mind tools.

Toolbox on ML and DL used in AI-Mind

Aim	To provide the basic knowledge on the technical use of AI-Mind Connector and Predictor. Mathematical expressions of limitations, uncertainties and explainability.
Audience	Clinicians, researchers, engineers, other interested healthcare professionals, patient organisations
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigated DL and ML approaches for the development of the AI-Connector and Predictor • Algorithm description, including mathematical limitations, uncertainties and the intention to explain the tool’s decision-making process • Platform architecture – the structure of the environment where the algorithms are hosted • Opportunities and limitations in using ML and DL in medicine • AI-Mind Connector’s and Predictor’s technical description for certification
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature • AI-Mind webinars - available online
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses/seminars on-site, hybrid and online • AI-Mind deliverables on these topics, including data preparation and feature extraction

Toolbox on EEG

Aim	To provide the basic knowledge for understanding high-density EEG, source reconstruction, noise reduction, feature extraction and the way electric signals are used in AI-Mind
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Audience	Engineers, researchers, clinicians (neurophysiologists, neurologists) other healthcare professionals
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The neurophysiological basis of EEG and technological details of 128 channel systems • Data preparation of empowered EEG • Empowered EEG based functional brain network theory • Source reconstruction on EEG
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-Mind webinars - available online • Equipment descriptions • Literature
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses/seminars on-site, hybrid and online • AI-Mind deliverables and other reports

3.2.4 Data management

To secure data privacy, it is important to ensure the proper data management on a high security server and the compliance with all applicable laws and regulations, nationally and in Europe. In this part, a toolbox with the basics of data governance of the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor's raw and pre-processed data is provided to clinicians and healthcare managers – among other stakeholders, for implementing the AI-Mind tools in a future new hospital setting.

Toolbox for data governance and sharing

Aim	To inform about the current data management procedures
Audience	Clinicians, healthcare managers, data protection officers and legal professionals, data scientists, IT directors, patient organisations, other healthcare professionals
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European regulations on data protection • AI-Mind project results (deliverables) • Data management & governance • Services for Sensitive Data (SSD) of the AI-Mind platform
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) • National laws • AI-Mind: Guidelines for data management and sharing (Data Governance Plan) (Deliverable 1.3) • AI-Mind: AI-Mind data governance and data management protection framework (Deliverable 1.4)
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses/seminars on-site, hybrid and online • Reports

3.2.5 Societal decision-making

Predictive HTA includes “all methods used to inform industry, health care providers and other stakeholders about the potential value of new medical products in development, including methods to quantify and manage uncertainty”¹ as a supplement to the long term HTA evaluation of the AI-Mind project. The purpose of this toolbox is to inform relevant stakeholders the earliest possible about the potential value and limitations of the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor and to support stakeholders’ decision-making for adopting the AI-Mind technology into the clinics. Clinical research will be able later to critically assess in population-based studies how an improved prediction rate of dementia in people with MCI will influence the health outcomes of individual patients and societies. Healthcare managers may assess how this influences the healthcare costs.

Toolbox on HTA of AI-based health technology

Aim	To inform about the importance of Health Technology Assessment (HTA) and decision-making analytical models on AI-based medical devices at the development phase. To support healthcare managers’ decision-making.
Audience	Clinicians, healthcare managers, policy makers, politicians, other stakeholders
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HTA framework for AI-Mind Decision analytical model used in AI-Mind for the prognosis of health outcomes and cost effectiveness
Material available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications AI-Mind: Health technology assessment framework for AI-Mind (Deliverable 6.1)
Material planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Webinar, courses/seminars on-site, hybrids and webinars Lectures and hands-on testing of decision analytical model with AI-Mind Connector and Predictor as a use case. AI-Mind deliverables

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5488152/>

4 User manuals for the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor tools

The educational guideline toolboxes described in the previous section create the knowledge-base for the use of both AI-Mind tools. In addition, a further, detailed guide with hands-on clinical procedure description of the Connector and Predictor will be created and made available to the national and later European communities of healthcare professionals. The user guidelines include:

- **Overall manuals for the use of AI-Mind Connector & Predictor:** step by step instructions for the use of the empowered EEG, digitalised cognitive testing and blood sampling procedures, software interfaces, and result interpretation;
- **Metadata collection handbook:** detailed procedure description for the collection of additional metadata that will be used in the Connector and Predictor: sociodemographic information, health status, comorbidities.

A preliminary overview of the user manuals for AI-Mind Connector and Predictor is shown in *Figure 3*. A detailed description of the manuals will be potentially revised and provided in the final version of this deliverable (deliverable 7.8 - “Final user guidelines for clinicians and scientific dissemination”, M60).

Figure 3: Structure of User Manuals for AI-Mind Connector & Predictor

5 The AI-Mind starter kit

The AI-Mind starter kit is developed in a two-step approach: the first step provides a starter kit for the AI-Mind clinical study and the second step is the final “starter kit” for the internal and external clinical users of the AI-Mind tools. The AI-Mind study starter kit was delivered to all clinical partners through the work done in WP2 and WP5 during 2021. The final AI-Mind potentially modified and approved “starter kit” is the evolution of the study starter kit, that will be designed focusing on the needs of external, non-research users of the AI-Mind technology and will be described in deliverable 7.7 (M60).

Clinical Study Starter Kit

A starter kit has been made available to all clinical sites in 2021 on the project internal platform before the initiation of the clinical study. It comprises material described in sections 3 and 4, covering a consensus background between the five clinical partners and the technical guidelines for the data collection. The study starter kit includes:

- **user guidelines:** handbook on data collection, video on blood sample collection, EEG recording video, tracking logs for various clinical study activities;
- **training exercises:** test sessions for the use of the digital NPT system (CANTAB) and its environment, observed and documented pilot EEG recordings, test sessions for the use of the electronic CRF pages (nettskjema);
- **general information on risk assessment and early intervention in people with dementia risk:** scientific publications, survey results on state-of-the-art diagnostic procedures and expectation towards AI based supportive decision making in the cohort of people with MCI (D1.1), MDR and AIA classification of the future AI-Mind Connector and Predictor tools (D1.2), Data Governance Plan (D1.4).

Figure 4 illustrates examples of practical instructions from the working document Data Collection Handbook used in the AI-Mind clinical study. To evolutionary improve the starter kit, all clinical partners are proactively encouraged to provide consecutively feedback from the beginning of the AI-Mind clinical study (in January 2022) at periodic intervals, e.g. twice a year.

Figure 4: Screenshots from Data Collection Handbook, created for the AI-Mind clinical study.

Final “AI-Mind Starter Kit”

The final version of the starter kit will be the evolution of the initial study starter kit and will include:

- the detailed user guidelines for AI-Mind Predictor and Connector (chapter 4);
- training exercises and other training material on empowered high-density EEG use, CANTAB testing, and blood sample collection;
- general information on risk assessment and early intervention on people at risk of developing dementia;
- links to user relevant online information as described in chapter 3.

It will be available for all clinicians and healthcare professionals on the project’s website (deliverable 7.7 – M60).

6 Conclusion

Deliverable 7.3 provides an outline of the guidelines for the users of AI-Mind Predictor and Connector. The objective is that the finally developed guidelines (D7.8) provide all the necessary material to inform the interested audience about the tools, their development and their use, in a practical and easy to handle way. The aim is to be transparent, supportive and motivating towards the AI-Mind tools’ use. The main focus is on clinicians and healthcare providers, but the stakeholders that may affect the decision-making in the adoption and use of the AI-Mind tools go beyond the clinical practice itself. Therefore, the guidelines, when developed, will take into account other stakeholder groups involved in the healthcare sector, which include – but are not limited to – healthcare managers, policy makers, politicians, IT engineers, and patient organisations.

The scope of this deliverable covers:

- i. the outline of the material that will create the knowledge base, implemented through the educational guideline programme and toolboxes,
- ii. the initial description of the practical user manuals for AI-Mind Connector and Predictor,
- iii. the description of the two-step development process of the AI-Mind starter kit.

This material will be developed throughout the project and the final user guidelines and starter kit will be submitted in M60 as deliverables 7.7 and 7.8.

7 Annex I – Educational material, example

Norwegian two-day course for General Practitioners: Improved and early initiated MCI diagnosis Programme outline (*programme translated from Norwegian; speakers and titles may be altered*)

Day I

Title: Presentation of the AI-Mind research project. What is MCI and who is the MCI patient? How to identify MCI? Speaker: Ira Haraldsen
Title: Challenges and opportunities with dementia assessment. Debate: Geir Selbæk and Gunhild Nytrøen
Title: Recent studies on incidence and modifiable risk factors, what do we know? Speaker: Geir Selbæk
Title: Panel discussion on challenges in identifying, investigating, and following up people with cognitive impairment. Discussion. Speaker: Anne Rita Øksengård. Panel: Rune Samdal and geriatric nurse Lillian Raaskjær
Title: Why are clinical trials important in a primary care perspective? A patient's experience of participating in a clinical study. Discussion. Speaker: Marte Kvittum Tangen. Co-speaker: TBA
Title: "The digital GP". Speaker: Anders Nyquist
Title: Introduction to MoCA with practical exercises. Speaker: Geir Selbæk
Title: i-Pad based cognitive testing - what can it be used for? Followed by discussion. Speaker: Christoffer Hatlestad-Hall
Title: Machine learning as a clinical tool - with focus on digital security, trustworthiness, data sharing and clinical utility. Discussion. Speaker: Mats Tvester, Thomas Tveitstøl and Ira Haraldsen
Summary and conclusions. Speaker: Ira Haraldsen

Day II

Title: Introduction and welcome. Speaker: Ira Haraldsen
Title: How to prevent harmful polypharmacy in the elderly? Review of drug compliance. Speaker: Morten Finckenhagen
Title: How to prevent harmful polypharmacy in the elderly? Medication management. Workshop. Speaker: Morten Finckenhagen
Title: Motivational interview (MI) as a tool to bring about patient change in general practice. Why MI? Research and experiences that form the basis of the method. Who can we use MI on? Speaker: Lars Linderøth
Title: What can MI be used by general practitioners? What qualities should you have / acquire as a general practitioner to get a good result? Speaker: Lars Linderøth
Title: Stages in change. What triggers change? Concrete techniques. Speaker: Lars Linderøth

Title: What is motivation? Conflicts that affect decision making. Resistance to change. Inhibitors and promoters. Speaker: Lars Linderoth
Title: The ambivalence cross as a method. Speaker: Lars Linderoth
Title: Motivational interview. Summary. <i>Speaker: Lars Linderoth</i>
Title: Conclusion and summary. Speaker: Ira Haraldsen